

Editorial of OSM Science 2024

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In August of this year, 2024, OpenStreetMap (OSM) celebrated its 20th birthday. OSM has grown from a small UK-based mapping project into the largest crowdsourced and volunteered geospatial database in the world. Here, as part of the seventh edition of the Academic Track at the annual State of the Map (SotM) conference, we celebrate the first global SotM on the continent of Africa. This year's OSM Science, as is the case with all previous editions of the Academic Track, delivers a consolidated knowledge hub for the gathering, sharing, and reporting of scientific progress in OSM-related research. Crucially, this platform facilitates the sharing of scientific findings about OSM directly with the broader OSM community. SotM 2024 takes place from the 6th to 8th September 2024 in Nairobi, Kenya with OSM Science and the Academic Track taking place on Sunday September 8th in its own dedicated session. There are 11 short papers corresponding to 7 full talks and 2 lightning talks presented at the conference with an additional 2 lightning talks presented as video talks. In this Editorial, we summarize these papers by briefly discussing their contributions and attempting to group these works into broad but also interrelated research topics. While this grouping reflects our own interpretation of the contributions and research outcomes of each paper, each extended abstract within the proceedings provides more details and information about the corresponding research. We encourage you to look at these works.

Zanchetta et al. [1] consider the challenge of assessing the performance of AI-assisted mapping of building footprints for OSM. Arising from the recent use of AI for mapping assistance in OSM, this work introduces fAIr ("Free and open source AI for Responsible mapping"): a fully open AI-assisted mapping service to generate semi-automated building footprints features developed by the Humanitarian OpenStreetMap Team (HOT). fAIr displays novelty in reintroducing the "human in the loop" for AI-assisted mapping. Currently, as reported by the authors, fAIr allows OSM mappers to create their own local training dataset, train/fine-tune a pre-trained Eff-UNet model, and then map directly within OSM with the assistance of their own local model. fAIr's performance is analyzed using twenty five urban regions and seeks to represent different grades of urban characteristics from different regions of the world. Within the domain of assessing the performance of various mapping approaches, Wang and Zipf [2] present their work on assessing the attribute accuracy and logical consistency of road data in OpenStreetMap.

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This work extends the substantial body of existing research work on OSM data quality by exploring quality dimensions specific to the case of motorized vehicle traffic. It does so by analyzing the attribute accuracy, i.e. whether tag values are available and correct, and logical consistency, i.e. topological correctness, of roads while taking into consideration country-specific laws and regulations. The framework is applied for Germany, relating mostly to speed limit data (in the context of attribute accuracy). Cohen and Nelson [3] also consider the transportation domain with their work on a methodological framework which combines OSMnx and a multilane detection algorithm to produce a Simplified OSM Data (SOD) network. The goal of this simplification process is to use the OSM data for improved active transportation analysis. The simplification relates to the combination of multiple transportation lanes related to active transportation (AT) into single centerlines, thus promoting the computation of various measures that relate to self-propelled human-powered travel modes, e.g. walking and cycling. Ways, in OSM, which share the same name, that show similarity in terms of orientation, and that are in close proximity to each other, are identified as multilane features. The approach is applied to several cities across the world, displaying varying levels of success.

Chukwu et al. [4] investigate the use of OSM data for disaster preparedness in Harare, Zimbabwe. Geospatial data about man-made structures and gasoline stations were added to OSM (where they were missing) and this data was then used to perform risk assessment analyses leading to the identification of danger zones and highly vulnerable areas, especially to fire hazards. Connected to disaster preparedness, Thomas [5] reflects on the outcomes and learning experiences of a Mini-Mapathon project, which involved 28 students within three Human Geography courses at an international high school in Beijing, China. Students were taught the basics of humanitarian mapping and then involved in real-world mapping projects using the Humanitarian OpenStreetMap Team's (HOT) Tasking Manager. A survey allowed the author to assess students' learnings as well as their motivation and future expectations to remain engaged in mapping projects. We also acknowledge the need to prepare for future climate scenarios and improve sustainability in our interactions with the environment. With this in mind, Lo Presti and Mooney [6] report on an analysis of renewable energy infrastructure representations in OpenStreetMap. To support the renewable energy transition there is a constant need for availability of reliable data about renewable energy infrastructure. In this work, the authors argue that OSM can meet these demands but it is necessary to identify common mapping errors and tagging issues associated with wind and solar energy infrastructures representation within OSM to ensure data quality. The work also presents the results of a geographical analysis to consider the distribution of infrastructures across various land cover types, seeking to detect patterns around land cover and renewable energy infrastructures. Ireland and Belgium are considered in the analysis but extension to more regions and areas is planned in the future. A further example of the use of OSM in the research process is proposed by Strus et al. [7], who involved a group of university students in adding data to OSM through a mix of sources: field mapping using mobile apps, high-resolution imagery, external sources such as scientific publications and a GPS receiver. In addition to providing students with the necessary knowledge to become experienced OSM contributors, the maps generated in this way are then used as a basis for multiple studies in the hydrogeological and urban planning domains.

Tockner et al. [8] consider the changing trends in the global evolution of corporate mapping in OSM. In this work, the authors provide an analysis from continuously monitoring

the impact of large corporate contributors to OSM in regards to their changing patterns of contributions. This is very important towards supporting a stronger, data-driven, understanding of the sustainability of OSM in the longer term. Following on from existing research, this work presents analysis to quantify the impact of corporate editing, particularly on volunteer mapping behavior, as an important measure of the structure and robustness of the OSM community. Along the same theme, Hoferek et al. [9] investigates corporate editors in OSM by considering the demographic makeup, careers, motivations and community relationships of the OSM contributors belonging to corporate editors. Results of a survey indicated multiple groups of corporate editors. Although interesting results on the corporate editors' profiles may be extracted the authors concede that a higher rate of participation from corporate editors in these types of surveys is required to ensure better overall representation. The role of humanitarian projects is often considered in the same conversations as those of corporate editors. In this vein, Rossi [10] describes research on examining how crowd-mapping and PGIS (Participatory GIS) could turn out to be a crucial tool in contributing to humanitarian projects, such as HOTOSM, by playing a role in shaping participatory processes. Fieldwork, reported as part of the research, includes an emergency intervention led by a five NGOs consortium project. The team participated in the HOTOSM Project by mapping different polygons/buildings delimiting territorial areas hit by the earthquake, as a part of an initiative by the Open Mapping Hub for West and Northern Africa. The final paper in our proceedings by Grinberger and Minghini [11] reflects on a systems perspective analysis of the events behind the introduction of rate limiting in OSM. This work uses a specific case in OSM's history – a set of politically-motivated edits deleting and distorting OSM data in Israel – to discuss the vulnerabilities and resilience-enhancing capabilities of the project. By tracing how the reactions to these events had led to the formation of a temporary coalition between the local mapping community and the data working group that was eventually used to mobilize support for a project-wide change - the introduction of a daily rate limit – it shows that the basic assumptions of OSM simultaneously increases the project's vulnerability and promotes resilience.

Overall, our proceedings reflect a wide range of topics, from AI tool application and data quality to sustainability, education, and humanitarian applications. As with SotM conferences of the past, this year's conference continues to demonstrate the diverse and impactful research being conducted within the OSM community. It is thus with great excitement that we look to the future of research with and about OSM, hoping that this OSM Science 2024 meeting will continue to provide contributions to shape and explore the field of scientific exploration of OSM and its long-term research agenda.

References

- [1] Zanchetta, A., Sharma, K., & Najjar, O. (2024) Assessing the performance of AI-assisted mapping of building footprints for OSM. In: Minghini, M., Grinberger, A. Y., & Mooney, P. (Eds.) *Proceedings of OSM Science 2024*, Nairobi, Kenya, 6-8 September 2024, 17–21.
- [2] Wang, W., & Zipf, A. (2024) Assessing the attribute accuracy and logical consistency of road data in OpenStreetMap. In: Minghini, M., Grinberger, A. Y., & Mooney, P. (Eds.) *Proceedings of OSM Science 2024*, Nairobi, Kenya, 6-8 September 2024, 45–48.
- [3] Cohen, A., & Nelson, T. (2024) From Complexity to Clarity: Simplifying OpenStreetMap Data for Improved Active Transportation Analysis. In: Minghini, M., Grinberger, A. Y., & Mooney, P. (Eds.) *Proceedings of OSM Science 2024*, Nairobi, Kenya, 6-8 September 2024, 30–33.

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- [4] Chika Chukuw, K., Pondon, L., & Paradzayi, C. (2024) Analyzing the Spatial Distribution of Fuel Stations in Harare, Zimbabwe: Leveraging OpenStreetMap for Disaster Preparedness, Mitigation and Recovery. In: Minghini, M., Grinberger, A. Y., & Mooney, P. (Eds.) *Proceedings of OSM Science 2024*, Nairobi, Kenya, 6-8 September 2024, 13–16.
- [5] Thomas, J. (2024) Crisis Mapping: Teaching High School ELL Students How To Make Maps That Save Lives. In: Minghini, M., Grinberger, A. Y., & Mooney, P. (Eds.) *Proceedings of OSM Science 2024*, Nairobi, Kenya, 6-8 September 2024, 5–8.
- [6] Lo Presti, L., & Mooney, P. (2024) Analysis of renewable energy infrastructure representations in OpenStreetMap. In: Minghini, M., Grinberger, A. Y., & Mooney, P. (Eds.) *Proceedings of OSM Science 2024*, Nairobi, Kenya, 6-8 September 2024, 26–29.
- [7] Strus, P., Górska, A., Brzyski, W., Bobrek, A., & Konderak, N. (2024) Beyond the seventh mountain, beyond the seventh river - OpenStreetMap as a base map in geographical research. In: Minghini, M., Grinberger, A. Y., & Mooney, P. (Eds.) *Proceedings of OSM Science 2024*, Nairobi, Kenya, 6-8 September 2024, 34–36.
- [8] Tockner, L., Herfort, B., Lautenbach, S. (2024) Shifting trends in global evolution of corporate mapping in OSM. In: Minghini, M., Grinberger, A. Y., & Mooney, P. (Eds.) *Proceedings of OSM Science 2024*, Nairobi, Kenya, 6-8 September 2024, 22–25.
- [9] Hoferek, A., Soden, R., & Sarkar, D. (2024) Investigating Corporate Editors in OpenStreetMap. In: Minghini, M., Grinberger, A. Y., & Mooney, P. (Eds.) *Proceedings of OSM Science 2024*, Nairobi, Kenya, 6-8 September 2024, 41–44.
- [10] Rossi, V. (2024) The role of crowd-mapping and PGIS in post-emergency humanitarian operations. In: Minghini, M., Grinberger, A. Y., & Mooney, P. (Eds.) *Proceedings of OSM Science 2024*, Nairobi, Kenya, 6-8 September 2024, 9–12.
- [11] Grinberger, A.Y., & Minghini, M. (2024) What happens when VGI is threatened? An analysis of the events behind the introduction of rate limiting in OpenStreetMap. In: Minghini, M., Grinberger, A. Y., & Mooney, P. (Eds.) *Proceedings of OSM Science 2024*, Nairobi, Kenya, 6-8 September 2024, 37–40.